

Relative Rates of Oxidation of Some L-Hydroxy Acids by Ceric Sulphate

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The rates of oxidation of Glycollic, Lactic, L-Hydroxy iso-Butyric, Malic, Mandelic and Citric acid have been studied kinetically at different temperatures and at different hydrogen ion concentrations. No significant increase in the rate of oxidation with increase in the concentration of H^+ ion at constant bisulphate ion concentration. The rate of oxidation of glycollic acid is found to be slowest and that of citric acid is fastest under similar conditions. Energy of activation of all the acids are found to be 20 ± 1 K.Cals. The entropy of activation of all the acids have been also calculated.

The kinetics of oxidation of glycollic¹, L-hydroxy iso-Butyric², lactic acids⁴ etc. have been studied by large number of scientists. The relative rates of oxidation of some L-Hydroxy acids by ceric sulphate have been studied by Kemp and Waters³ but the work of Kemp and Waters does not account for the difference in rates of oxidation of these acids. The present study is taken to include two more acids and reason for their difference in rate of oxidation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reactions were carried out in glass stoppered bottles at constant temperature. The temperature was maintained to $\pm 0.02^\circ$. The reactive substances were brought to thermostate temperature and then rapidly mixed in reaction bottles also at previously brought to the thermostate temperature. The cerium (IV) solution was last to be added. The zero-time of the reaction was noted when half of the cerium (IV) solution was in the reaction bottle. Aliquots were withdrawn at known intervals of time and reaction quenched by adding the aliquots to the known excess of ferrous ions, was then back titrated against standard cerium (IV) solution with ferroin used as an indicator. Addition of sodium perchlorate, potassium nitrate or sodium chloride did not make a significant decrease in rate of oxidation. No attempt was therefore, made to keep the ionic strength of the reaction mixture constant.

Effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the rate of oxidation was studied by varying the hydrogen ion concentration by addition of perchloric acid at constant bisulphate ion. To eliminate complications due to changes in ionic strength of the solution it was adjusted by addition of sodium perchlorate. The experimental results showed that increase in concentration of H^+ ion caused no significant increase in the rates of oxidation in these acids at higher concentration of bisulphate ions.

The value of rate constant K , in all cases found to be independent of the changes in the initial concentration of Cerium (IV) when the concentration of H^+ and HSO_4^- are kept constant.

TABLE 1

(a) *Glycollic Acid*Glycollic : $0.50 M$ Ce(IV) : $9.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ H_2SO_4 : $0.442 M$

Temperature $0^\circ C$	Temperature $0^\circ A$	$K_1 \times 10^4$ Sec $^{-1}$
35	308	5.86
40	313	10.00
45	318	16.14

TABLE 2

(b) *Lactic Acid*Lactic Acid : $5.00 \times 10^{-2} M$ Ce(IV) : $4.38 \times 10^{-3} M$ H_2SO_4 : $0.62 M$

Temperature $0^\circ C$	Temperature $0^\circ A$	$K_1 \times 10^4$ Sec $^{-1}$
30	303	2.52
35	308	4.05
40	313	6.90
45	318	10.90

TABLE 3

(c) *L-Hydroxy-iso-butyric Acid*L-hydroxy iso-butyric acid : $3.00 \times 10^{-2} M$ Ce(IV) : $4.38 \times 10^{-3} M$ H_2SO_4 : $0.62 M$

Temperature $0^\circ C$	Temperature $0^\circ A$	$K_1 \times 10^4$ Sec $^{-1}$
30.5	303.5	4.78
35.0	308.5	8.15
40.0	313.0	14.20
45.0	318.0	23.50

TABLE 4

(d) *Malic Acid*Malic Acid— $3.00 \times 10^{-2} M$ Ce(IV)— $4.91 \times 10^{-3} M$ H_2SO_4 — $1.18 M$

Temperature 0°C	Temperature 0°A	$K_1 \times 10^4$ Sec ⁻¹
35	308	5.84
40	313	10.00
45	318	16.10

TABLE 5

(e) *Mandelic Acid*Mandelic Acid— $7.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ Ce(IV)— $4.92 \times 10^{-3} M$ H_2SO_4 — $1.40 M$

Temperature 0°C	Temperature 0°A	$K_1 \times 10^4$ Sec ⁻¹
35	308	13.8
40	313	22.8
45	318	38.0

TABLE 6

(f) *Citric Acid*Citric Acid— $1.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ Ce(IV)— $4.38 \times 10^{-3} M$ H_2SO_4 — $1.14 M$

Temperature 0°C	Temperature 0°A	$K_1 \times 10^4$ Sec ⁻¹
30.7	303.7	7.94
35	308	13.2
40	313	23.0
45	318	35.8

The second order rate constant $\left(K = \frac{K_1}{\text{Hydroxy acid}} \right)$ of these acids at $1.4 M$ sulphuric acid concentration at 35° were found to be as in the Table 7.

TABLE 7

(H ₂ SO ₄) = 1.40 M Acid	Temperature 35° litre mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
Glycollic	0.253 × 10 ⁻³
Lactic	2.46 × 10 ⁻³
L-Hydroxy-iso-butyric	9.63 × 10 ⁻³
Malic	15.4 × 10 ⁻³
Mandelic	171.0 × 10 ⁻³
Citric	584.0 × 10 ⁻³

The energy of activation of these acids were also calculated. Table 8 gives values of the energy of activation *PZ* value and entropy of activation.

TABLE 8

Acid	ΔE (K:Cal/mole)	PZ (Litre-mole ⁻¹) Sec ⁻¹	ΔS E.U.
Glycollic	20.4 ± 1.0	3.85 × 10 ¹¹	-6.4
Lactic	19.4 ± 1.0	5.23 × 10 ¹¹	-5.8
L-Hydroxy iso-butyric	20.6 ± 1.0	1.118 × 10 ¹³	+5.09
Malic	20.8 ± 1.0	1.4 × 10 ¹³	+6.3
Mandlic	19.6 ± 1.0	1.17 × 10 ¹³	+7.8
Citric	20.9 ± 1.0	5.87 × 10 ¹⁴	+8.04

DISCUSSION

The rates of oxidation follow the order Citric > Mandelic > Malic > L-hydroxy-iso-butyric > Lactic > Glycollic. The observed value of rate constants *K* of Table 7 for glycollic, lactic, mandelic and L-hydroxy-iso-butyric acids are of the same order as those reported by Kemp and Waters³. The values of *K* reported by Kemp and Waters³ refers to 25° and (H₂SO₄) 1.66 *M* while the values of *K* reported here refer to 35° and (H₂SO₄) = 1.4 *M*.

The energy of activation and entropy of activation for the oxidation of these acids have been calculated and reported in Table 8. Energy of activation for all these acids have been found to be almost of constant value. The entropy of activation of glycollic and lactic acid is found to be negative whereas in the case of L-hydroxy-iso-butyric acid, malic, mandelic and citric acid is found to be positive. These differences in the rates of oxidation of these acids must be due to the operation of polar and steric influences.

The rates of oxidation of glycollic, lactic, L-hydroxy-iso-butyric, and mandelic acids are much more alike differing only by a factor which can easily be attributed to the effect of substituent group R, in facilitating the formation of radical HOOR₂ i.e. *pH* >> CH₃ > H. However, a comparison of the rates of oxidation of lactic, malic, L-hydroxy-iso-butyric and citric acid suggest that polar factor alone are not enough to account for the difference of the rates of oxidation. It therefore, appears, that the increased rate of oxidation of malic and citric acid may be traced to the steric influences.

REFERENCES

1. G. V. Bakore, R. Dayal and P. Nath, *Z. Physik Chem.*, 1964, **19**, 227.
2. R. Dayal and G. V. Bakore, *Z. Physik Chem.* Communicated.
3. T. J. Kemp and W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 1192.
4. K. P. Bhargava, R. Shanker and S. N. Joshi, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, **21B**, 573.
5. R. Dayal, K. K. Banerji and G. V. Bokore, *Indian J. Chem.* 1972, **9**, 1017